

Using the Quantity $z(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{m})$ in Terms of General Relativity

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Abstract

Albert Einstein's general theory of relativity describes gravitation through a deformation of space-time. However, there is a high degree of parallelism between the linear approximation of general relativity and Maxwell's theory of electromagnetism. Both theories are absolutely equivalent to each other in the linear derivation. Therefore, mass and charge have analogous positions and functions. This is the starting point for considering that it should be possible to combine both theories into one. To do so, the general theory of relativity has to be formulated for the quantity z , which is a complex number that combines mass and charge. In this way, it becomes possible to combine general relativity and electromagnetism into one theory.

Introduction

The concepts of electromagnetism and gravitomagnetism have been described in relation to seeking the equivalence of gravitational and electromagnetic phenomena [1]. The gravitational field in gravitomagnetism is equated to an electromagnetic field with similar attributes in electromagnetism. The gravitational field is used to describe the interaction between moving objects, just as the electromagnetic field is used to describe the interaction between moving charges [2]. In this regard, the gravitational field is generated by the masses of objects, while the electromagnetic field is generated by charges. These two fields are explained by analogous sets of mathematical equations. Electromagnetism and gravitomagnetism can be described with the classical theorem hypothesizing that every object with mass defines its occupancy of space based on its emission of mass and energy at a rate proportionate to the mass that moves away from it at the speed of light and carries data on the velocity, position and electric charge status of the object [3]. This review explores gravitomagnetism and electromagnetism, focusing on the parallelism and homology of electromagnetism based on Maxwellian theory and the first linear approximation of the Einsteinian field equations of general relativity to gravitomagnetism.

Using the Einsteinian Theory of General Relativity in a Maxwellian Theory

Gravitoelectromagnetism (GEM) explains gravitational effects on objects in motion [4]. Based on approximations of intermediate fields, the homology and parallelism between electromagnetism and GEM can be demonstrated by expressing the first linear approximation of the Einstein field equations of general relativity in a Maxwellian theory analogous to the

equations of electromagnetism [5]. Essentially, every electromagnetic field is linked to a gravitational field and is composed of a gravitoelectric and a gravitomagnetic field. Considering that both fields share an origin in the particle, the electric field and magnetic field can be described via their analogs of gravitational perspectives involving the coefficient of proportionality k [6]. The proportionality coefficient is dependent on the mass and charge ratios and on the charge exhibited between the gravitomagnetic permeability and electromagnetic permittivity. The coefficient of coupling can be increased by means of a high ion current or nuclear or electron spin alignment [7].

Leaving aside the effects associated with special relativity and spatial curvature, the theory of general relativity, which explains gravitation, can be described with a linear approximation of the Einsteinian field equation, which has a structure analogous to the Maxwell equations defining electromagnetism [8,9]. The approximation of the weak fields, the intermediates, divides gravitation into elements comparable to magnetic and electric fields. Whereas massive objects exhibit attracting or repelling forces towards or away from each other depending on their electric charges, the analogous structure between the electromagnetic field and gravitational field generates a coupling whose existence is based on the origin of both fields [10, 11]. In this regard, the gravitational field originates from particulate mass, while the electromagnetic field originates from particulate charge [12-14]. While a particle is in motion, a gravitomagnetic field and an electromagnetic field are created simultaneously. As such, the gravitomagnetic field can be induced analogously to the electromagnetic field exerted on the particulate object [15].

The derivation of the weak field approximation is given by the analogs of electromagnetism and gravitomagnetism based on the assumption that objects in motion move at speeds lower than that of light, meaning that special relativity can be neglected [16]. Second, the potential and/or kinetic energies of all objects under consideration are smaller than their mass energy, such that the effects of spatial curvature can be neglected. Third, the weakness of gravitational fields is such that it validates superposition, and the space between objects is minimal; thus, retardation can be neglected [17]. The expression of the linear approximation entailing the Einstein general relativity theory starts with the following equation [18,19]:

$$R_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\alpha\beta}R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\alpha\beta} \quad (1)$$

Under the given assumptions, approximations of metrics can be formulated with the indices α and β set to 0, 1, 2, and 3 and $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ set to (+1, -1, -1, -1) to denote the metric tensor describing flat spacetime [20]. The condition $|h_{\alpha\beta}| \ll 1$ has been used to describe the flat metric variation such that this metric approximation of the Ricci tensor and scalar is applied with:

$$R_{\alpha\beta} \cong -\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{c^2}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \Delta\right)h_{\alpha\beta} \quad (2)$$

$$R \cong \eta^{\alpha\beta}R_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{c^2}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \Delta\right)h \quad (3)$$

From the above equations, a coordinate system can be described using a gauge condition $h_{\alpha\beta}$ leading to the definition of the gravitational potential of an object $\ddot{h}_{\alpha\beta}$. Substituting equations 2 and 3 into 1, the weak field equation is derived as:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \hat{h}_{\alpha\beta} - \Delta \hat{h}_{\alpha\beta} = -\frac{16\pi G}{c^4} T_{\alpha\beta} \quad (4)$$

To generate the gravitational analogs by expressing them using the Einstein-Maxwell equations to elucidate the vector-scalar potential, the energy-momentum tensor is used in the first approximation with order zero assuming that different measures do not vary with time [20]. Therefore, the derivative of time in the gravitational potential is marked at zero with different energy-momentum components set to zero, excluding $T_{00} = \rho_m c^2$, where ρ_m denotes the mass density. As a result, the weak field equation deduced above is transformed into the Poisson equation. The gravitational analog in the equation is denoted by Φ_g in the representation of the scalar potential, while the gravitational permittivity is denoted by ϵ_g , leading to the definition of the Newtonian gravitational constant G .

Exploring the first order of a higher approximation for the energy-momentum tensor, the assumption that the potential does not vary with time holds when massive objects are in constant motion maintaining a particular linear velocity. An additional energy-momentum component is denoted by T_{0i} , and based on the deduced weak field equation, a vector potential analog is defined in terms of the mass density flow, denoted by $\vec{A}_g$ [20]. In the equation, the gravitomagnetic permeability μ_g is expressed as:

$$\mu_g = \frac{4\pi G}{c^2} = 9.31 \times 10^{-27} \frac{m}{kg} \quad (5)$$

Taking gravitational waves to travel at the speed of light, analogously to electromagnetic waves, the gravitomagnetic field ($\dot{B}_g$) and gravitoelectric ($\dot{g}$) field are determined. On rearranging the deduced weak field equation to obtain the Maxwellian structure, a Maxwell-Einstein equation is derived (18, 20). The rearrangement is not dependent on the initial assumption that prohibits time variation in the gravitational potential $h_{\alpha\beta}$, so the time dependence of A_g is permitted. Nevertheless, the determination of the vector potential and gravitational scalar are not defined. The homology and parallelism of electromagnetism following the Maxwell theory and the first linear approximation of the Einsteinian field equation of general relativity leading to gravitomagnetism are defined by the comparison between the derived Maxwell-Einstein equation and the Maxwell equations of electromagnetism.

Maxwell equations of electromagnetism:

$$\text{div } \bar{\mathbf{E}} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{div } \dot{\mathbf{B}} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{rot } \bar{\mathbf{E}} = - \frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{B}}}{\partial t} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{rot } \dot{\mathbf{B}} = \mu_0 \rho \tilde{\mathbf{v}} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{E}}}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

Maxwell-Einstein equations of gravitomagnetism:

$$\operatorname{div} \bar{\mathbf{g}} = -\frac{\rho_m}{\epsilon_g} \quad (10)$$

$$\operatorname{div} \dot{\mathbf{B}}_g = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\operatorname{rot} \bar{\mathbf{g}} = -\frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{B}}_g}{\partial t} \quad (12)$$

$$\operatorname{rot} \dot{\mathbf{B}}_g = -\mu_0 \rho_m \tilde{\mathbf{v}} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{g}}}{\partial t} \quad (13)$$

In the above derivation, the distinct integrals of volume described in the equations are based on point masses. Modifications will need to be made to the integrals for massive objects with large volumes. As described above, the similarity between the gravitomagnetic equations considering the Maxwellian theory of electromagnetism is possible based on linear approximations of the Einstein field equations.

Introduction of the quantity z into general relativity

There is a high degree of parallelism and agreement between the Maxwell formulas for electromagnetism and the equations resulting from a linear approximation of the Einsteinian field equations for gravitation, as presented here.

Therefore, there is a high degree of parallelism between electromagnetism according to Maxwell and gravitation according to the theory of general relativity (GRT) of Einstein.

To recognize this parallelism, one must form the first linear approximation of the Einsteinian field equations. This linear approximation then shows a high degree of parallelism with Maxwell's equations for electromagnetism. Conversely, this also means that both theories and their corresponding sets of equations (Maxwell and Einstein) can be combined into one:

$$z = (bq, m) = bq + mi \quad \text{with} \quad b = \text{const} \quad (14)$$

$$z = \left(bq, \frac{E}{c^2}\right) = bq + \frac{Ei}{c^2} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{z}{v} = \frac{\left(bq, \frac{E}{c^2}\right)}{v} = \frac{bq}{v} + \frac{Ei}{vc^2} = b \left(\frac{q}{v}\right) + \left(\frac{E}{v}\right) \frac{i}{c^2} \quad (16)$$

with the related Newtonian equations:

$$F_{z,z} = G \frac{z_1 z_2}{r^2} \quad (17)$$

$$E_{z,z} = -G \frac{z_1 z_2}{r} \quad (18)$$

This single summarized theory and the corresponding equations can be obtained by introducing the quantity z instead of the mass and/or energy into the Einsteinian field equations of gravitation

or by substituting the z -density (i.e., z per volume) instead of the mass and/or energy density into the Einsteinian field equations of gravitation.

With the size z and/or the z -density, a modification of the Einsteinian field equations results, which contains and explains both electromagnetism and gravitation at the same time.

Since z consists of an imaginary part and a real part, the resulting two partial equations, which do not mutually affect each other for electromagnetism and gravity, both influence each other and do not influence each other, while the respective terms remain side by side. In addition, however, terms arise in which electromagnetism and gravitation directly influence each other.

Within the framework of the GRT, the size z can be considered as a kind of combined charge and energy magnitude, and the z -density is a kind of combined charge and energy density; this is because the GRT is based on the principle of the equivalence of gravitational and inertial mass (which is questionable and remains to be experimentally checked) and the equivalence of mass and energy.

If one introduces the quantity z or the z -density into the Einsteinian field equations and then takes the linear approximation, then gravitomagnetism follows from these equations as naturally as do Maxwell's equations of electromagnetism.

Conversely, this also means that there is an opportunity to test the new theory obtained in this way in practice.

If Einstein's field equations for gravitation are more exact than Newton's equations for gravity, then the Einstein field equations with the size z (or with the z -density) should also be more exact for electromagnetism than the Maxwell equations.

We should therefore be able to obtain a more precise formulation of electromagnetism with the z -substituted Einsteinian field equations than is allowed by the Maxwell equations.

The difference should be experimentally investigable and confirmable.

At the same time, this can be of great help if electromagnetism can be formulated in a more precise way, e.g., for predicting and calculating the current flow in miniaturized electronic circuits. Moreover, it is extremely important to have a more exact formulation because we are extremely dependent on electromagnetism in all of our technical applications.

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